

Region dependent ultrafast FRET in an ionic liquid-P123 gel : A femtosecond study[†]

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Abstract : Ultrafast forster resonance energy transfer (FRET) in a RTIL-P123 gel is studied by femtosecond up-conversion technique. The mixed gel consists of a tri-block copolymer, (PEO)₂₀-(PPO)₇₀-(PEO)₂₀ and a room temperature ionic liquid (RTIL) (1-pentyl-3-methyl-imidazolium bromide, [pmim][Br]). The acceptor rhodamine 6G (R6G) being ionic, stays in the peripheral corona region of the micellar aggregates of the gel. We use two donor dyes of different hydrophobicity. The hydrophobic neutral donor coumarin 153 (C153) resides in the core while the hydrophilic ionic donor coumarin 343 (C343) is located in the corona. As a result donor-acceptor distances are different for the two donors. Thus by varying the donor one can study region dependent FRET processes in the RTIL-P123 gel.

Keywords : Femtosecond, spectroscopy, FRET, ionic liquid, Tri-block copolymer gel.

1. Introduction

According to Forster theory, the rate of forster resonance energy transfer (FRET) is inversely proportional to the sixth power of donor-acceptor distance¹. Thus when the donor and the acceptor molecule are at close proximity, FRET is expected to occur on an ultrafast time scale. Ultrafast FRET at short distances play a key role in light harvesting systems^{2,3}, between organic dyes bound to nanoparticles⁴⁻⁷, and between nano-particles and bases in DNA⁸. We have previously studied ultrafast FRET in micelles^{9,10}, mixed micelles¹¹, microemulsion¹², vesicles¹³ and in a non-polar octa-acid capsule¹⁴. FRET from tryptophan to hypericin was investigated by Petrich and co-workers¹⁵. Most recently, many groups applied single molecule FRET to study protein folding^{16,17}, structure of enzyme substrate complex¹⁸ and other biological issues^{19,20}.

Many organized assemblies are heterogeneous in molecular length scale. Donors and acceptors of different polarity are located in different regions of such assemblies. We have previously employed excitation wavelength variation to probe FRET in different regions⁹⁻¹³. In the present work, we report region dependent FRET process in an RTIL-P123 gel using two donor dyes – (a hydrophobic dye coumarin 153, C153 and an hydrophilic ionic

dye coumarin 343, C343) of different hydrophobicity and an ionic dye R6G as an acceptor.

We have studied this in a gel consisting of a tri-block copolymer (PEO)₂₀-(PPO)₇₀-(PEO)₂₀ (Pluronic P123) in the presence and absence of a room temperature ionic liquid. In an aqueous solution at a low concentration P123 forms a micelle with a hydrophobic PPO core and a hydrophilic PEO corona^{21,22}. At a sufficiently high concentration, successive dehydration of the PPO blocks of the P123 tri-block copolymer results in a close packed crystalline gel phase (Scheme 1A)²³⁻²⁷. The structure of the gel involves interpenetration of the micelles and intermicellar entanglement (Scheme 1A). In the gel phase ~48% of the total space is “void” and is occupied by water. Castner and co-workers studied the temperature-dependent micellization and gel formation in Pluronic F88 tri-block copolymers and estimated the microscopic friction in different region of these systems using picosecond fluorescence anisotropy decay²⁸. We have previously studied diffusion in different region of the P123 and F127 gel using Fluorescence Correlation Spectroscopy (FCS)²⁹. Very recently we have shown that addition of a RTIL to a P123 gel keeps the gel intact and we have studied diffusion in the RTIL-P123 gel³⁰.

In the present work we report on FRET in different

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

Scheme 1. Structures of (A) P123 gel, (B) Coumarin 153 (C153), (C) Coumarin 343 (C343), (D) Rhodamine 6G (R6G) dye.

region of the P123 gel. In this case, the ionic acceptor rhodamine 6G (R6G) stays in the peripheral corona region close to the ionic donor C343 and exhibits very fast FRET. The hydrophobic donor C153 stays in the PPO core far from R6G.

2. Experimental section

Laser grade dyes coumarin 153 (C153, Exciton; Scheme 1B), coumarin 343 (C343, Exciton; Scheme 1C) and rhodamine 6G (R6G, Exciton; Scheme 1D) were used as received. The tri-block copolymer, Pluronic P123 was a gift from BASF Corp. and used without further purification. We used 30 wt % of P123 for the gel phase (Scheme 1A). The gel was prepared by mixing a proper amount of

P123 with 100 mL of water. The solution was kept at a low temperature ($\sim 0^\circ\text{C}$) and stirred for 8–10 h using a magnetic stirrer in a sealed container. Subsequently, the solution was kept in a refrigerator for a week. 1-Methylimidazole (99%, Aldrich) and 1-bromopentane (99%, Aldrich) were used for the synthesis of the room-temperature ionic liquid (RTIL). Dichloromethane (Merck) was used as received. Diethyl ether (Merck) was distilled over KOH. The RTIL was synthesized following the sonochemical route³¹ as described earlier¹². The steady-state absorption and emission spectra were recorded in a Shimadzu UV-2401 spectrophotometer and a Spex FluoroMax-3 spectrofluorimeter, respectively. All experiments were done at room temperature (293 K). Our

up-conversion setup (FOG 100, CDP; IRF ~ 350 fs) and picosecond a TCSPC setup (IRF ~ 90 ps) described earlier³². Following Forster theory, the rate of FRET (k_{FRET}) was calculated as¹

$$k_{\text{FRET}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{rise}}^{\text{A}}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{D}}^0} \left(\frac{R_0}{R_{\text{DA}}} \right)^6 \quad (1)$$

where τ_{D}^0 is the lifetime of the donor in the absence of acceptor and $\tau_{\text{rise}}^{\text{A}}$ is the rise time of acceptor emission in the presence of donor. At a donor-acceptor distance $R_{\text{DA}} = R_0$, the efficiency of energy transfer is 50% and $k_{\text{FRET}} = (1/\tau_{\text{D}}^0)$. To calculate the Forster distance R_0 (Å), we used¹

$$R_0 = 0.211[\kappa^2 n^{-4} Q_{\text{D}} J(\lambda)]^{1/6}$$

where n is the refractive index of the medium (~ 1.4 for macromolecules in water)¹, Q_{D} is the quantum yield of the donor in the absence of acceptor, κ^2 is the orientation factor, and $J(\lambda)$ is the spectral overlap between the donor

emission and the acceptor absorption. $J(\lambda)$ is related to the normalized fluorescence intensity (F_{D}) of the donor in the absence of the acceptor and the extinction coefficient of the acceptor (ϵ_{A}) as¹

$$J(\lambda) = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} F_{\text{D}}(\lambda) \epsilon_{\text{A}}(\lambda) \lambda^4 d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} F_{\text{D}}(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (3)$$

In this work, we used $\kappa^2 = 2/3$ (random orientation) for the calculation of R_0 ³².

3. Results

3.1. Steady state study of FRET

The emission spectra of the donors (C153 and C343) both in presence and absence of R6G are shown in Fig. 1. The emission maximum of hydrophobic neutral C153 dye (506 nm) in 30% P123 gel are found to be

Fig. 1. Emission spectrum of 20 μM C153 and C343 in the absence (—) and in the presence of 40 μM R6G (-----) (at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm) in 30% P123 gel and in 30% P123 gel in the presence of 0.3 M and 0.9 M RTIL. Emission spectrum of 40 μM R6G in absence of donors (C153 and C343) in each case has been shown (.....).

blue-shifted by 44 nm from the emission maximum (550 nm) in bulk water³³. The blue shift of the emission maximum is ascribed to lower polarity in the core of the P123 gel. The emission maximum of hydrophilic anionic probe C343 (488 nm) in 30% P123 gel are found to be similar to that (488 nm) in bulk water³⁴. This indicates that the polarity of the corona region is similar to bulk water. With the addition of RTIL, the emission maximum of C153 remains almost constant but the emission maximum of C343 gradually blue shifted from 490 nm (in 30% P123 gel) to 484 nm in presence of 0.3 M RTIL and to 481 nm in presence of 0.9 M RTIL.

For the acceptor (R6G), the absorption maximum is at 526 nm in bulk water and displays a red shift to 534 nm in 30% P123 gel. Emission maximum of R6G exhibits a red shift from 550 nm in bulk water to 569 nm in 30% P123 gel. In the gel phase, R6G may reside at the corona or in the "void" space between the micelles.

Fig. 2 shows the overlap between the absorption spectrum of the acceptor (R6G) and the emission spectrum of

the donors (C153 and C343) in different systems. The values of spectral overlap integral, $J(\lambda)$, between the emission spectrum of the donors and absorption spectrum of acceptor at different systems are listed in Table 1. The spectral overlap $J(\lambda)$ for C153 dye is greater than that of C343 dye for all the three different systems. Thus the extent of quenching is smaller for C343 compared to that of the C153. Table 1 also lists Forster distance R_0 of different systems. We have calculated the steady-state efficiency (ϵ) of FRET using the relation, $\epsilon = 1 - (I_{DA}/I_D)$. I_{DA} and I_D are the steady state emission intensity of the donor in the presence and absence of the acceptor, respectively¹⁰. The steady state efficiency of FRET (ϵ) for different systems are summarized in Table 1.

3.2. Time resolved studies

3.2.1. Picosecond studies :

FRET is commonly monitored by shortening of donor lifetime. However, the donor emission is dominated by the unquenched non-FRET donors and hence no shorten-

Fig. 2. Overlap spectra between donor emission (C153 and C343) (—) with acceptor absorption (R6G) (-----) in different systems at $\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm.

Table 1. Energy transfer parameters for FRET-pair in different system at $\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm

System	FRET pair	λ_{em} of Donor (nm)	$J(\lambda)^a$ ($M^{-1} cm^1 nm^4$)	R_0^a (Å)	$\epsilon,^a$
30 wt% P123	C153-R6G	508	3.98×10^{15}	62.6	51.5
	C343-R6G	488	2.95×10^{15}	61.4	40
30 wt% P123 + 0.3 M [pmim][Br]	C153-R6G	506	3.67×10^{15}	58.2	64
	C343-R6G	484	2.74×10^{15}	65.67	62
30 wt% P123 + 0.9 M [pmim][Br]	C153-R6G	507	3.83×10^{15}	57.5	65.2
	C343-R6G	481	2.81×10^{15}	61.7	33

^a $\pm 10\%$

ing of the donor lifetime is detected in a picosecond setup. Since the picosecond decay of the donor does not correctly describe the ultrafast FRET, we monitored FRET from the rise of the acceptor emission. In this section we report the long component of FRET detected in a pico-

second setup. In the next section, we will discuss detection of the ultrafast component of FRET using a femtosecond setup.

Fig. 3 shows the picosecond fluorescence transients of the acceptor (R6G) alone and in the presence C153

Fig. 3. Picosecond transients ($\lambda_{em} = 570$ nm) of the acceptor (R6G) in absence (A) and presence of donor (C153 and C343, D + 30% P123 gel and in 30% P123 gel in presence of 0.3 M and 0.9 M RTIL at $\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm.

and C343 as donor. We have studied the fluorescence transient of the acceptor (R6G) at $\lambda_{em} = 570$ nm. At this wavelength, the contribution of the quenched emission of the donor is negligible. In the absence of the donors (C153/C343), the acceptor (R6G) exhibits a single exponential decay (~ 4500 – 5000 ps) with no rise component in all cases. However, in the presence of donor (C153/C343), picosecond transients of the acceptor (R6G) at 570 nm show distinct rise components for both the donor molecules in all the three systems (30% P123 gel, 30% P123 gel with 0.3 M [pmim][Br] and in 30% P123 gel with 0.9 M [pmim][Br]). The observed rise components are ascribed to the FRET from donor molecules (C153/C343) to acceptor molecule (R6G).

In 30% P123 gel, we have detected two rise times of 450 ps and 2600 ps for C153 as a donor and 300 ps and 3500 ps for C343 as a donor. In the presence of 0.3 M [pmim][Br], the corresponding rise times are 600 ps and 3220 ps (for C153) and 200 ps and 3950 ps (for C343). In the presence of 0.9 M [pmim][Br], the rise times become 470 ps and 3430 ps (for C153) and 350 ps and 3535 ps (for C343), respectively (Table 2).

0.3 M [pmim][Br], the rise components become 46 ps (for C153) and 2.5 ps (for C343) and in the presence of 0.9 M [pmim][Br], 10 ps (for C153) and 1.7 ps (for C343) rise time components are obtained (Table 3). Note, in the absence of donor, no rise component is observed in the acceptor emission (Fig. 4) in P123 gel alone and in presence of 0.3 M and 0.9 M RTIL. Comparison of the femtosecond transients of the rise of the acceptor in presence of the donor (C153 and C343) both in presence and absence of RTIL are shown in Fig. 5. Fig. 5 clearly depicts the differences in the rise of the acceptor emission in different systems. In the following section, we will discuss the origin of the ultrafast component of FRET and explain how the hydrophobic C153 and hydrophilic C343 donor molecule reports region dependence FRET process inside the RTIL-P123 gel.

4. Discussion

The main findings of this work may be summarized as follows. This work demonstrates that femtosecond spectroscopy is a very sensitive tool to detect ultrafast FRET between a donor and an acceptor bound to a mixed gel. From the rise time of the acceptor emission we detected three different time constants of FRET ~ 1 – 50 ps, ~ 200 –

Table 2. Picosecond decay parameters of R6G (40 μ M, $\lambda_{em} = 570$ nm) in the absence and presence of C153 and C343 (20 μ M) at $\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm in different system

System	Donor	τ_1^a (a_1) (ps)	τ_2^a (a_2) (ps)	τ_3^a (a_3) (ps)
30 wt% P123	C153	450 (–0.10)	2600 (–0.37)	6400 (1.47)
	C343	300 (–0.14)	3500 (–2.77)	5920 (3.91)
30 wt% P123 + 0.3 M [pmim][Br]	C153	600 (–0.22)	3220 (–0.93)	6400 (2.15)
	C343	200 (–1.80)	3950 (–6.66)	5600 (9.46)
30 wt% P123 + 0.9 M [pmim][Br]	C153	470 (–0.21)	3430 (–1.26)	5830 (2.47)
	C343	350 (–0.09)	3535 (–2.57)	5470 (3.66)

^a $\pm 10\%$

3.2.2. Femtosecond studies :

The ultrafast components of FRET were detected by using a femtosecond setup. Fig. 4 shows the ultrafast rise of the acceptor (R6G) at an emission wavelength of 570 nm in presence of two different donor molecules (C153 and C343). We have detected ultrafast rise component of 30 ps (C153 as donor molecule) and 1 ps (C343 as donor molecule) for 30% P123 gel (Table 3). In the presence of

600 ps and a very long one at ~ 2600 – 3500 ps.

From the time constant of FRET, the donor-acceptor distances, R_{DA} , were calculated using eq. (1) (Table 4). The multiple time scale may be ascribed to a distribution of donor-acceptor distances. These time scales correspond to three distinct D-A distances for each systems for both the donor-acceptor pair. These distances are smaller than the size of the mixed gel.

Fig. 4. Femtosecond transients of the acceptor (R6G) emission ($\lambda_{em} = 570$ nm) in the absence (\circ) and in the presence (Δ) of the donor (C153 and C343) in 30% P123 gel, 30% P123 gel in presence of 0.3 M RTIL and in 30% P123 gel in presence of 0.9 M RTIL for both the C153 and C343 donor dyes at $\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm.

Table 3. Femtosecond decay parameters of R6G (40 μ M, $\lambda_{em} = 570$ nm) in the presence of C153 and C343 (20 μ M) at $\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm in different system

System	Donor	τ_1^a (a_1) (ps)	τ_2^a (a_2) (ps)	τ_3^a (a_3) (ps)	τ_4^a (a_4) (ps)
30 wt% P123	C153	30 (-0.12, 16%)	450 (-0.28, 20%)	2600 (-0.80, 64%)	6400 (2.20)
	C343	1 (-0.19, 21%)	300 (-0.21, 23%)	3500 (-0.50, 56%)	5920 (1.90)
30 wt% P123 + 0.3 M [pmim][Br]	C153	46 (-0.33, 24%)	600 (-0.15, 11%)	3220 (-0.90, 65%)	6400 (2.38)
	C343	2.5 (-0.13, 14%)	200 (-0.22, 23%)	3950 (-0.60, 67%)	5600 (1.95)
30 wt% P123 + 0.9 M [pmim][Br]	C153	10 (-0.15, 21%)	470 (-0.20, 29%)	3430 (-0.35, 50%)	5830 (1.7)
	C343	1.7 (-0.21, 16%)	350 (-0.48, 36%)	3535 (-0.65, 48%)	5470 (2.34)

^a $\pm 10\%$

Fig. 5. Comparison of femtosecond rise of the acceptor (R6G) ($\lambda_{em} = 570$ nm) in 30% P123 gel (o), 30% P123 gel in presence of 0.3 M RTIL (Δ) and in 30% P123 gel in presence of 0.9 M RTIL (\diamond) for both the C153 and C343 donor dyes at $\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm.

Table 4. Donor-Acceptor distances in different system calculated from the rise time of acceptor emission

System	Donor and acceptor pair	τ_{FRET} (ps)	R_{DA} (Å)
30 wt% P123	C153-R6G	30, 450, 2600	26, 41, 55
	C343-R6G	1, 300, 3500	15, 39, 59
30 wt% P123 +	C153-R6G	46, 600, 3220	27, 41, 54
0.3 M [pmim][Br]	C343-R6G	2.5, 200, 3950	19, 39, 64
30 wt% P123 +	C153-R6G	10, 470, 3430	20, 38, 54
0.9 M [pmim][Br]	C343-R6G	1.7, 350, 3535	17, 40, 60

Let us first compare the fastest component of FRET for C343 and C153 as donor. In the absence of RTIL, the fastest components are 1 ps for C343 and 30 ps for C153. They correspond to donor-acceptor distances of 15 Å and 26 Å respectively. The shorter D-A distance for C343 may be attributed to the fact that both the ionic donor C343 and the ionic acceptor R6G are located in the polar corona region close to each other. In the case of the hydrophobic donor C153, the donor stays in the core while the acceptor stays in the corona and hence, the distance is

large (26 Å).

In 0.3 M RTIL the magnitude of the shortest component increases to 2.5 ps for C343 and 46 ps for C153 increasing the donor acceptor distance to 19 Å and 27 Å respectively. It seems the ions of the RTIL partially offset the attractive interaction of the C343 anion and the R6G cation and the D-A distance increases. The effect of this interaction is less for the neutral donor C153 and hence the D-A distance remains unaffected.

In 0.9 M RTIL the components for C153 (10 ps) is somewhat closer to that (1.7 ps) for C343. In this case the donor-acceptor distances are quite close (17 Å for C343 and 20 Å for C153). It appears that at this high concentration, the RTIL invades both core and corona region of the P123 gel and this reduces the difference between the two regions. Thus the difference in rate of FRET decreases for the two donors.

It may be noted in all cases there are long components of FRET which corresponds to D-A distances of 40–50 Å. These distances are less than the radius of the P123 micellar aggregate present in the gel (~90 Å) and may arise from FRET between donor and acceptor in different sides (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Schematic diagrams of different Donor-Acceptor pair in P123 micellar aggregate.

5. Conclusion

This work demonstrates two donor dyes of different hydrophobicity reports different region dependent FRET processes in the core and in the peripheral corona region

of RTIL-P123 gel. The time components of FRET are markedly affected by RTIL i.e. RTIL penetrates the core of P123 gel and modifies the structure.

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